
Need and Importance of Green Accounting for Sustainable Development

Dr. Naganath Dnyanoba Banasode

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce and Management

Savitribai Phule Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Satara

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15147309

Abstract:

In today's world, many companies are facing numerous environmental problems due to their focus on maximizing profits, the increasing demands of consumers, rapid advancements in technology, and the unsustainable consumption of natural resources. Corporate sustainability has become one of the biggest challenges for these companies. Therefore, this study aims to explore how accounting, as the language of business and a source of information are important for sustainability. The research paper investigates different approaches to corporate sustainability using Green Accounting. Through continuous efforts to find the most suitable accounting system for sustainable development, green accounting has emerged as a potential indicator of sustainability. This research article relies on primarily as well as secondary data and modern accounting practices. It also provides a methodology and data types that can help improve the green accounting system in India and promote sustainable development in the corporate sector.

Keywords: *Need of Green Accounting, Eco-Accounting, Green Accounting System, and Sustainable Development.*

Introduction:

Green accounting is related to environmental aspects, information and environmental eco-auditing systems it has been defined as the identification, tracking, analysis, and re- porting of the materials and cost information associated with the environmental aspects of an organization. Green accounting is relatively modern and a developing field. However, in India the green accounting is considered at an infant stage because, the implementation of green accounting in organizations. But, in India lack of awareness, lack of green and ethical education and so on. The primary role of green accounting is to attempt the social environmental problems.

Green Accounting which also takes social and environmental factors into consideration that has been given several names over the last few years, including, for

example, environmental accounting, triple bottom line accounting, and sustainable accounting. India has been facing the twin problems like protecting the environment and promoting economic growth. Responsibility towards environment has become one of the most crucial areas of social responsibility. Concern over environmental and land degradation has grown in recent years. This degradation is mostly caused by many forms of pollution, such as soil erosion, deforestation, water and air pollution, and sound pollution. These issues are becoming a global occurrence. In addition to harming human health, this issue lowers economic output and results in a loss of amenities. Determining dependable revenues that are also ecologically sustainable is a challenge for corporate sectors. Environmental accounting is widely accepted in green accounting.

Transparency in accounting about environmental expenses is known as "green accounting." It lists the expenses and advantages that an organisation experiences as a result of its involvement in environmental-related activities. The identification, measurement, and distribution of environmental costs, their incorporation into business operations, the recognition of environmental liabilities, and the dissemination of the results to the company's stakeholders as part of financial statements are all typically included in green accounting. Additionally, e-commerce helps to advance and improve green accounting.

Statement of the Problem:

One of the most important tools for understanding how the environment affects the economy is green accounting. Green accounting provides data that highlights the contribution of natural resources to economic growth and the costs associated with pollution or resource degradation. Businesses should devote some of their resources to ecological balance and environmental preservation. As a result, it is expected that corporate organisations will take into account the use of items that may be environmentally harmful. In India, green accounting is still in its infancy. Some companies are creating a separate environmental policy department, putting pollution control measures into place, following applicable rules and regulations, and providing enough information on environmental factors in their annual reports. There are several difficulties in environmental accounting and reporting, including the method of environmental accounting. This research paper aims to know the need and importance of green accounting practices for sustainable development.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study components and aspects of green accounting.
2. To study the how green accounting important for sustainable development.
3. To study the advantages and disadvantages of Green Accounting.

Research Methodology:

Primary Data: The primary data required for the study was collected from the accountants. With the help of questionnaire for study purpose.

Secondary Data: Secondary data was collected through various books, journals, magazines.

Sample Design: The Researcher adopted convenient sampling method for the selection of accountants. Those relating to the accounting works and they are using green accounting for their organizations.

Sample Size: Researcher selected 50 respondents for his study. The criteria for selection of the sample were the organizations were using green accounting system in their organization in last two or more years.

Scope of Green Accounting:

Green accounting involves estimation of environmental expenditures, capitalization of those environmental expenditures, identification of environmental liabilities and measurement of environmental liabilities. Environmental expenditures are expenses or costs related to environmental measures including production-related costs and product research and development expenditures which are incurred primarily for ensuring protection of environment. Environmental liabilities Obligation to pay future expenditure to remedy environmental damage that has occurred due to past events, activities or transactions or to compensate a third party that has suffered from damage. It

may even include a contingent environmental liability that depends on occurrence or non-occurrence of one or more future uncertain events or to compensate a third party that has suffered from such damage. These Green Accounting has the wide scope of sustaining business organizations and environment.

Types of Green Accounting:

A) Green management accounting: It involves the recognition, gathering, assessment, examination, internal documentation, and application of data related to materials and energy flow.

B) Green Financial Accounting: emphasizes the reporting of environmental liability expenses and other major environmental expenditures.

C) Green National Accounting: It emphasizes national resource stocks and the costs of externalities, among other factors.

Important Things To Use Of Green Accounting:

- Before implementing green accounting, a company must clearly define its accounting goals and environmental strategy.
- Assess the stakeholders, the organization's relationship with them, and the level of risk. Identify the environmental elements at work, how to quantify them, and the costs involved in achieving the goals.

- Acknowledge strategies for cost and resource reduction by encouraging innovative ideas. Continue using green accounting techniques to track the gradual decrease in environmental expenses.
- It is necessary to set up a personal account for environmental costs. It will help evaluate and communicate environmental effectiveness and spending.
- Expenses and benefits associated with environmental factors must be included in the income statement.
- It is necessary to establish an additional ecological value-added statement.

Limitation Of Green Accounting:

- There isn't a uniform accounting approach.
- It is not feasible to compare two countries or companies if their accounting methods and standards are differ.
- It primarily takes into account expenses within the company while excluding societal costs.
- Input for Green Accounting is difficult to obtain since costs and benefits related to the environment are hard to quantify.
- The initial expense for its tools and application is substantial.

Table No1: Age-wise Classification of Accountants

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage of respondents
25- 35	21	42%
36-45	12	24%
46-55	10	20%
Above	7	14%
Total	50	100

(Source: Compiled by Researchers)

Table No.1 revealed that the younger accountant is more engaged in green accounting. Because of advancement and its adoption is easier to understand of this age

group. It is observed that accountants in the age of 46 to 55 and above 55 are less used green accounting, because they believe old age or traditional accounting system.

Table No. 2: Gender Based Classification of Respondents

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage of respondents
Male	34	68%
Female	16	32%
Total	50	100

(Source: Compiled by Researchers)

Above table No.2 shows that the majority of the accountants are (68%) or interested in using green accounting according to their response. accountant male. Female accountant is not

Table No. 3: Category Based Classification of Respondents

Occupation	Number of Respondents	Percentage of respondents
Banking	9	18%
Hotel	11	22%
Retail Shop	13	26%
Education	7	14%
Construction	10	20%
Total	50	100%

(Source: Compiled by researchers)

Table No 3 indicate that among all the retailers are using green accounting regularly numbers (26%) because of time and money saving. Hoteliers also using the green accounting to their business and accountants are happy to use this accounting system. After the large number hotel users the education sectors also used green accounting of they also comfortable with these accounting.

Table No.4: Agreement Level of use of Green Accounting

Statement	1	2	3	4	5	Total Score	Mean Value	Percentile Value
Useful to Hotel Industry accounting	2	6	12	14	16	50	3.72	74.4
Weighted Score = (Satisfaction Level x No. of Respondents)	2	12	36	56	80	186		
Useful to Educational sector	5	10	12	18	5	50	3.16	63.2
Weighted Score = (Satisfaction Level x No. of Respondents)	5	20	36	72	25	158		
Useful to Construction accounting	10	9	8	16	7	50	3.02	60.4
Weighted Score = (Satisfaction Level x No. of Respondents)	10	18	24	64	35	151		
Useful to Banking accounting	8	9	17	11	5	50	2.92	58.4
Weighted Score = (Satisfaction Level x No. of Respondents)	8	18	51	44	25	146		
Useful to retail shop accounting	5	11	13	9	12	50	3.24	64.8
Weighted Score = (Satisfaction Level x No. of Respondents)	5	22	39	36	60	162		

(Source: Compiled by Researcher)

Table No. 4 shows the weighted score, mean and percentile value of using green accounting agreement level of green accounting. Agreement Level of use of Green Accounting Score 1 represent Strongly Dissatisfied Agree and score 5

Satisfaction Level (Weightages)	1	2	3	4	5
No of Respondents	2	6	12	14	16
Weighted Score = (Satisfaction Level x No. of Respondents)	2	12	36	56	80

$$\text{Mean Score} = \frac{\text{Total Weighted Score}}{\text{Total Sample}}$$

$$\text{Mean Score} = \frac{2+12+36+56+80}{50}$$

$\frac{186}{50} = \text{-----} = \mathbf{3.72}$

Total score 186 divided by No. of respondents 50= 3.72. The highest possible mean score 5=100%. Then mean score 3.72 = 74.40%.

The data reveals that about green accounting is useful to their industries or not the accountants give their responses 50 respondents have reported their responses regarding different types of industries is required or not the green accounting. 74.4 percent accountant agreed about green accounting is useful to the hotel industries. And 58.4 % accountant are reported their responses regarding agreement of use of green accounting to Banking industries.

Conclusion:

Green accounting practices are at a promising phase in India. The Indian corporate sector strives to comply with the terms and regulations concerning environmental protection. Currently, there

represent strongly agreed. For example, the score of first industry “Agreements about Hotel industry, Educational and retail as well as other sectors are trying to use” is ascertained as under.

are no well-defined policies established at the National, State, or even company level to guarantee adherence to environmental standards. Environmental accounting serves as a concrete instrument in implementing sustainable development. Green accounting is also necessary for the social accountability of businesses. The significance of environmental accounting is growing due to rising environmental issues, as well as economic, social, and technological advancements. This accounting method is achieved via environmental accounting. This accounting will make a significant contribution to sustainable development.

References:

1. Dr. Preeti Malik, D. A. (2015). A Study of Green Accounting Practices in India. *IRACST – International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management*, Vol. 4 (No.6), 779-787.
2. Hasan Senol, H. O. (2012). The Importance of Environmental Accounting in the Context of Sustainable Development and Within IFRS Evaluation . *International Symposium on Sustainable Development* , 81-88.
3. HERNÁDI, B. H. (2012). Green Accounting for Corporate Sustainability . *Club of Economics in Miskolc* , 23-30.

4. Krishna Moorthy, P. Y. (2013). Green Accounting: Cost Measures . *Open Journal of Accounting* , 4-7.
5. Roy, M. S. (2017). Green Accounting for Sustainable Development: Case Study of Industry Sector in West Bengal . *The Journal of Industrial Statistics* , 57-71.
6. Chauhan M., (2005). Concept of Environmental Accounting and Practice in India”, *The Chartered Accountant*, p.720-726.
7. Mrs. Payal Harsh (2020) Green Accounting Developments in India and its Significance *International Journal of Trend in Research and Development*, Volume 7(6), ISSN: 2394-9333
8. M. Bennett, P. James, Environmental-related management accounting; current practice and future trends. *Greener Management International* 1997; 17;33-51.
9. Adams Carol, Patty Mc Nicholas. Making a difference Sustainability reporting, accountability and organizational change. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*. 2006; 20(3):382-402
10. Alok Kumar, Pramanik (2002). *Environmental Accounting and Reporting*. Soujanya Books, Delhi.
11. Haripriya Gundimeda Pavan Sukhdev. Pushpam Kumar. Rajiv Sinha. And Sanjeev Sanya (2005). *TERI Press*, December
12. Mukesh Chauhan (2005), *Concept of Environmental Accounting and Practice in India*, *The Chartered Accountant* November 720- 726.